
Progress as a Problem: Strauss and Löwith in Dialogue between Antiquity and Modernity

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Abstract: In this paper I will make a comparison between the position of two thinkers of the 20th century on a specific issue, that is, the crisis of the modern idea of progress. These two German philosophers of Jewish origins were both educated in Weimar Germany, and they both were forced to flee from the Nazi-German persecution. They look at the problems of their present with a critical eye oriented towards the research of their origins and they both find, in a certain retrieval of the ancient thought, a way out from the contradiction of Modernity. In the first part I will show the analysis proposed by Leo Strauss and Karl Löwith of a shared problem: the modern idea of progress. They both give an analytical insight of a concept that, otherwise, could be understood in a generic way. Furthermore, they both refer to the contemporary crisis of this idea and propose different ways to tackle philosophically the problem. In the second part I will articulate their respective criticisms to the *belief* in progress through the reference to the ancients. In the first place I will go back to their sources, then I will analyze the different meaning attached to their “antiquity turn”: hermeneutical radicality on the one hand, sense of limit and measure on the other¹.

Keywords: Progress, Strauss, Löwith, Return, Antiquity

1. The crisis of the modern idea of progress

After the historical trauma of the Second World War, philosophy was challenged to understand the roots of this tragedy and to inquire into the mistakes made by Modernity in its self-knowledge. One of the main features of modern thought is the idea of progress which, for centuries, inspired and guided philosophy, science and common understanding. Both Strauss and Löwith start their inquiry from a statement of fact: the crisis of the modern idea of progress, a problem that philosophy cannot ignore anymore².

In his lecture *Progress or Return?* Strauss begins abruptly as following:

The title of this lecture indicates that progress has become a problem - that it could seem as if progress has led us to the brink of an abyss, and it is therefore necessary to consider alternatives to it. For example, *to stop* where we are or else, if this should be impossible, *to return*.³

This quotation is already a strong position followed by an alternative regarding the issue of progress: the idea of progress led to disastrous consequences in human history, and we have to decide whether to stop where we are or to return. As we will see, this alternative expresses the positions of the two thinkers here in comparison.

In his *The fatality of Progress* Löwith gives a voice to a similar description of the matter: «In the general conscience the faith in progress has been put in doubt only after the First World War»⁴. In fact «the moment when the first atom bomb has been dropped no one can avoid the fatal dilemma of progress»⁵. We can express this dilemma as follows: «The question is whether there is an instance that can limit the unlimited progress or if it is inevitable that *man does anything that he can do*»⁶.

According to the two authors, thanks to modern science man has improved his power and control over nature to an unprecedented point. Nonetheless, his «wisdom and goodness»⁷ did not grow accordingly, and man revealed blind to the good or bad use of his potentialities. This kind of blindness appears a consequence of the gradual substitution of the distinction «good-bad» with the distinction «progressive-reactionary»⁸. But historical experiences proved the content of the idea of progress to be wrong, thus revealing its fideistic nature. The observation of this shift in the consideration of the idea of progress already dominated the academic debate, as Strauss wrote:

A generation or so ago, the most famous study on this subject was entitled *The Idea of Progress*. Its opposite number in present-day literature is entitled *The Belief in Progress*. The substitution of belief for idea is in itself worthy of note.⁹

The idea of progress, which has been the pivotal idea of modern Western civilization, appears in a crucial crisis: in order to criticize it, a full account of its elements is needed.

Strauss and Löwith's essays show a useful and meaningful analysis of the elements of the modern idea of progress, showing its fideistic implications and with a substantial agreement in their analysis. However, their discussions of the concept differ slightly in that they put different emphasis on particular aspects of the modern idea of progress, and this affects their subsequent interpretations. It is now convenient to schematize the results of the analysis given by the two authors to spur the similarities and the differences in their understanding of the concept.

According to Strauss, we can summarize the elements characterizing the modern idea of progress as follows¹⁰:

- Progress is change towards an end. This end is conceived as a certain kind of intellectual perfection. The very model of the movement towards the future perfection of the understanding is given by the improvement made by the arts and crafts from the beginning of human existence onwards. This improvement provides also the idea of the very imperfect beginning of human condition. To sum up: progress is a movement towards a future perfection of human understanding.
- The entire development of human thought is conceived as a progressive one.
- Modern thought, from XVIIth century on, represents an absolute progress: Modernity conceives itself as a break from the past and looks backwards aware of its own superiority.
- There is a fundamental and necessary parallelism between intellectual and social progress¹¹.
- Intellectual and social progress knows no limits.
- Infinite intellectual and social progress is actually possible.
- Every stage of development reached by humankind represents a secured acquisition, beneath which it is impossible to fall¹².
- There is a close connection between the idea of progress and that of conquest of nature: nature has to be subjugated to the power of men, in order to improve their existence on Earth. The model of this kind of attitude is Francis Bacon¹³.
- The best way to tame nature is natural science, which gains honor and importance over all the other kinds of knowledge. As a result, philosophy has lost its preeminence and its authoritative role.

In *The Fatality of Progress* Karl Löwith's analysis offers some additional elements:

- There is a conceptual distinction between development and progress. Development is defined as a natural change towards a fixed goal (*télos*), as it is the case of biological development of an individual from birth to adulthood. Progress, instead, is defined as change without a fixed end, or with an indefinite end: this kind of open change typically belongs to the human world and it is a product of culture.
- The peculiarity of progress stems from human natural tendency towards the modification and appropriation of nature. According to Strauss this tendency evolves in modern times into the progressive domination of nature.
- Modern progress has its peculiar rhythm: every new acquisition becomes soon something given for granted, and the longing for new acquisitions immediately moves forwards the process. Like desire, progress wants always *more*, for its very constitution prevents itself from resting quietly in what it acquires. This almost neurotic movement onwards and the characteristic addiction to the products of progress are connected with the economics at the basis of their diffusion: the liberal and capitalistic economy¹⁴. In this scenario «the longing for progress becomes, in turn,

progress»¹⁵. In short, we can define the features of progress as an example of bad infinity.

- The willingness of progress is combined with the fatalistic sense of its unavailability and with a blind hope in its continuous improvement¹⁶. This observation is connected with the interpretation, given by Löwith, of belief in progress as a part of a larger philosophy of history, according to which «history in itself and as a whole performs a continuous movement onwards as progress towards a goal»¹⁷. Löwith sharply criticizes this conception, which for him characterizes the entire Western thought from the Christian era onwards.

To sum up, the modern belief in progress is oriented to the future and open to an infinite movement towards a better state. It also involves the belief in the possibility of realizing such an open goal and it is willing to pursue it. The modern belief in progress involves a fatalistic certainty that this kind of infinite improvement is actually unavoidable. This kind of acritical certainty towards the idea of progress shows the fideistic nature of the idea itself. According to the modern belief in progress, there is a necessary link between progress in scientific and technical knowledge and progress in the social conditions. To conclude, modern belief in progress involves the optimistic certainty of the stability of men's accomplishments.

Both Strauss and Löwith open to an answer to this philosophical question by addressing the ancient thought. To understand better the meaning of such a move, it is necessary, in the first place, to highlight their sources.

2. Back to the Ancients?

In dealing with the problem of modern faith in progress Strauss and Löwith both invoke the ancient thought. This operation is twofolded: in the first place, they investigate the ancient meaning of the concept of progress, highlighting this way its distance from the modern idea of progress. Secondly, the two authors advance a retrieval of the ancient way of thinking as an alternative from the crisis of Modernity. The problem is that they both give very few references and they use very large generalization, leaving the reader the task to specify their references. It is thus necessary to make some clarifications regarding their sources, in order to better understand the philosophical meaning of their proposal.

In discussing the characteristics of the ancient concept of progress, Strauss refers directly to just two passages of Aristotle *Politics*. In addition, he only mentions Seneca and Lucretius, sparing himself the quotation of precise passages¹⁸. The first reference to Aristotle refers to the possibility of an infinite progress within the *technai*:

[...] the art of medicine is without limit in respect of health, and each of the arts is without limit in respect of its end for they desire to produce that in the highest degree possible, whereas they are not without limit as regards the means to their end for with all of them the end is a limit to the means.¹⁹

According to Strauss, the same idea is to be found in Seneca and Lucretius. It is possible to spur referencens regarding this topic scattered in the work of Seneca, for example in his *Epistulae morales ad Lucilium*:

Hence I worship the discoveries of wisdom and their discoverers; to enter, as it were, into the inheritance of many predecessors is a delight. It was for me that they laid up this treasure; it was for me that they toiled. But we should play the part of a careful householder; we should increase what we have inherited. This inheritance shall pass from me to my descendants larger than before. Much still remains to do, and much will always remain, and he who shall be born a thousand ages hence will not be barred from his opportunity of adding something further.²⁰

As far as Lucretius is concerned, the reference is the fifth book of the *De rerum natura*, in which the progress of men on the path of civilization is presented up to the «highest pinnacle» of the development of arts and techniques:

All these [arts] as men progressed gradually step by step were taught by practice and the experience of the active mind. [...] For they saw one thing after another grow clear in their minds, until they attained the supreme pinnacle [*summum cacumen*] of the arts.²¹

Löwith too invokes Lucretius, although he disagrees with Strauss regarding the possibility to find there the concept of an *infinite* progress in human knowledge, given the fact that their limit is given precisely by the supreme pinnacle or *summum cacumen* named in the last line of the quotation above²².

As we have seen, Strauss highlights, on the one hand, the presence of the idea in the Ancient thought of an infinite progress in human knowledge, gradual and sometimes open to an indefinite movement onwards. He also makes a general reference to Plato, according to which «the fulfillment proper, namely full wisdom, is not possible but only quest for wisdom which in Greek means philosophy»²³. But, on the other hand, there is a substantial difference between *technai* in general and the *politiké téchne*. This difference, which is crucial in the characterization of the Ancient way of thinking in comparison to the modern one, is stressed by Strauss by turning once again to Aristotle. The latter discusses the opportunity of making changes in the laws and the institution to improve them, i.e. to realise better the purpose of the *politiké téchne*. However

[...] to change the practice of an art is a different thing from altering a law; for the law has no power to compel obedience beside the force of custom, and custom only grows up in long lapse of time, so that lightly to change from the existing laws to other new laws is to weaken the power of the law.²⁴

Strauss adds another element to the ancient understanding of the concept of progress, namely the common belief according to which the world is periodically subjected to natural cataclysms, an idea shared by the authors quoted above²⁵.

As we have already seen, the main references in Löwith's essay are Lucretius and the myth of Prometheus. In both cases the philosopher finds a general awareness of

the progress made by men in the fields of the *technai* and of the social organisation. However, those progresses are not systematized into a more general conception of a movement of history towards improvement: instead, they are simply observed as a characteristics of human existence. Löwith stresses in particular the ancient awareness of the perils brought about by every new discovery. In other words, the ancients were aware of the other side of the coin of every innovation, regarding which they had no illusions. We can find a statement of this sentiment in Lucretius' work:

So man in vain futilities toils on / Forever and wastes in idle cares his years/Because, of very truth, he hath not learnt / What the true end of getting is, nor yet / At all how far true pleasure may increase. / And 'tis desire for better and for more / Hath carried by degrees mortality / Out onward to the deep, and roused up / From the far bottom mighty waves of war.²⁶

But for Löwith the best exemplification of this kind of awareness in the Ancient thought is given by the myth of Prometheus. In Aeschylus' *Prometheus Bound*, Prometheus speaks about the knowledge and gifts he gave to humans beings, stressing the fact that they don't suffice in protecting him and humans from gods' anger and Fate: «Skill is weaker by far than Necessity»²⁷. As Löwith states, «In Greece there has never been blunt exaltation of technical power»²⁸.

It is clear that, for both Löwith and Strauss, addressing the ancients involves the grouping of considerations taken from authors, who are very distant in time and space, in order to create a general thought on the matter. From this point of view, the analysis does not aim at a detailed historical account: what really matters is the creation of a contrast between Antiquity and Modernity. This contrast aims to be specular to the one that is characteristic of the self-understanding of Modernity, although in the case of Strauss and Löwith the Antiquity ought to emerge as the positive term of comparison.

Both the accounts of Strauss and Löwith show a substantial agreement on the general understanding of a certain kind of progress by the ancients. Briefly, a concept of progress is to be found in the Antiquity, but this concept does not imply the belief in progress. Accordingly, in the ancient thought there is the conscience of progress in knowledge and even of an infinite one, at least potentially. This kind of progress in knowledge and understanding is, however, limited to the sphere of some *technai*. Also, the idea of the development of mankind from the early stages of the primitive state towards civilization is a common place in the ancient thinking. Thus, in denying, as the two authors do, that the ancients had the idea of progress does not mean to deprive them of conscience of the gradual development of mankind in knowledge and civilization²⁹: instead, it means that these elements do not combine with the other features of the modern idea of progress, thus implying the *faith* in progress³⁰.

By making reference to Aristotle's *Politics*, Leo Strauss stresses the absence of the link, which is crucial for the modern belief in progress, between technical-scientific and social progress: according to his interpretation of *Politics* 1268 b 26 ff., the *polis* needs stability, not inno-

vation, therefore it is not obvious to state an analogy between the other *technai* and the *politiké techné*.

As far as Löwith is concerned, he highlights the Hellenistic ideal of measure and limit in opposition to the infinite movement of the modern belief in progress. Sir Francis Bacon expressed his preference for *plus ultra* as the new guiding maxim of the new era against the old delphic motto *non plus ultra*³¹ inherited from the Ancients: on the contrary, to Löwith is precisely the instance of limit that has to be recovered from the Antiquity.

Both for Löwith and Strauss the ancient concept of progress has to be understood together with a general understanding of human nature as a stable entity, which is conceived as only a part of a larger whole, that of a *kosmos* where mankind has no infinite time to pursue its enterprises: the world is subject to recurrent natural disasters that cyclically interrupt the path of the alleged progress, and that periodically force humanity to start over and over from an earlier stage of achievements³².

At this point of my analysis, two questions have to be raised: which kind of Antiquity is the one evoked by the two authors? What is the philosophical meaning of their turning to the Ancient thought? It is easy to see that their generalization of Antiquity³³ could very well be criticized by using different references from those they refer to. But the value of this generalization lies precisely in its capacity to encompass a very large period, separated from the following times by an epochal change. The more general issue here is the rupture represented by Christianity and the modifications it involved in the image of man and his relationships with Nature and Cosmos. After the irruption of Christianity on the scene of history and thought, man has begun to look at himself as the center of creation, a creation that is meant to be at his disposal. In what precedes this epochal hiatus, man was conceived as an indifferent being for the whole of *kosmos*, and this view provided him with a very different attitude towards his behaviour and expectations³⁴.

In the following section, I will try and show the way in which this very general view on the matter acquires a more specific meaning for the two authors.

Besides the similarities in the analysis of Strauss and Löwith, there are important differences in the way they conceive the philosophical meaning of taking back the ancient thought into consideration. Their disagreement on the matter is a recurrent topic of their correspondence: as Strauss wrote to Löwith, «it is astonishing that, beyond a certain point, we understand each other so badly, when until that point we understand each other so well»³⁵.

What are the reasons of this mutual misunderstanding? ³⁶ In the first place, we can find in Strauss an attention to the peculiar declination of the idea of progress in the Jewish context, which is foreign to Löwith's interests³⁷. In this context, progress has a meaning related to the idea of critical detachment from the Jewish tradition and of assimilation: this process was presented as a progress compared to tradition, but the very idea turned out to be a fatal deceit, as Strauss points out in quite the same terms as Gershom Scholem³⁸. This particular case of the general crisis of the belief in progress offers Strauss a critical concept in opposition to the idea of progress: the Jewish concept *T'shuvah*, repentance. Twisting this concept, Strauss deprives it of its religious meaning and in-

terprets it as "return", specifically return from a wrong path to the right one. "Return" implies, in opposition to the idea of progress, the superiority of the beginnings over what follows. If in the religious sphere this conception entails the superior authority of the theological tradition, in the philosophical field one should rather go back to a certain way of *questioning* the tradition, namely the Socratic attitude towards the traditions and beliefs of the common way of thinking.

In his essay on Collingwood's *The Idea of History*³⁹, Strauss states that in taking the ancients into consideration one should also allow for the possibility that they had a proper understanding of the «fundamental problems», an understanding we have lost⁴⁰. This lack of understanding is for Strauss a sign of intellectual decline, made worse by the fact that this age considers this loss a progress. In such a condition, the only progress available to these times would be going back to an understanding of the ancient thought without the burden of contemporary assumptions, an understanding able to disclose the fundamental questions and to show their value, independently from the historical periods⁴¹.

Thus, the reference to the concept of *T'shuvah* is not simply an additional element to the Straussian reasoning: instead, it represents the philosophical usage of a category of the Jewish faith, understood as a return to an ancient path: a path of reasoning, not a religious one. This is a conceptual tool taken from a completely different context; Strauss uses it as an alternative to the modern idea of progress. However, it is possible to spur a residual trace of repentance in the concept of *T'shuvah* as return: something went wrong, because we have forgotten the right path. This is what we ought to admit in the first place to regain what we have lost. The philosophical process of returning to the Ancient thought changes those who enact it: it is not a blunt restoration, but a return from another place which enriches those who undertake the quest, giving them a point of view from which they can truly criticize the present time. As Strauss wrote:

By the very fact that he seriously attempts to understand the thought of the past, he leaves the present. He embarks on a journey whose end is hidden from him. He is not likely to return to the shores of his time as exactly the same man who departed from them. His criticism may very well amount to a criticism of present day thought from the point of view of the thought of the past.⁴²

There is a double movement working here: returning to the ancient way of thinking, in the one direction, and back to the present time in the other. The possibility to enact such a radical kind of hermeneutics, with the opposition between return and progress, is a matter of debate between Strauss and Löwith. Discussions about this subject appear all over the entire correspondence between Strauss and Löwith since the 30s, showing the crucial importance of this problem for the two thinkers.

By taking the ancients into consideration Löwith looks for a conception of time as "eternal present", as opposed to the look towards the future typical of the entire understanding of history which, in his interpretation, we have inherited from Christianity. Löwith finds this kind of awareness in the composure of Hellenistic philosophies.

The problem of how one conceives time intersects that of the conception of nature. From the Christian and post-Christian point of view, nature is something humankind can dispose of, which for Löwith is a disastrous way of thinking, because it provides no limits to the modern appropriation of nature by men⁴³.

In contrast, Löwith aspires to

reach one day [...] the old manner of Late Antiquity (stoic-epicurean-skeptical-cynical), a life-related, really viable wisdom, to reach the “close things” and not the far ones, which are the object of dreaming of history, in the future as well in the past. However, the German and the Jews lack the sense of the present – of the *nunc stans* – of “noon and eternity”.⁴⁴

But what moves this research of a quiet detachment, of a wise retirement in imperturbable calm, is actually a fierce polemic against the present point of view and the tradition that gave birth to it. This unilateral negation falls again, or at least risks falling, into the same conceptual scheme it breaks from. This kind of polemical moderation is connected with the sense of an impossible detachment from one’s historical situation. This, in turn, entails the idea that philosophical problems bring their historical collocation:

You are [...] wrong, if you think that Nietzsche, or any of us “modern”, can simply leave aside his “being conditioned by modern premises” and so – in principle – can “repeat” *ancient antiquity*.⁴⁵

In Strauss’s eyes this idea is typical of the historicist understanding, which he criticizes in all his philosophical production. In turn, the Straussian return to the Ancients is for Löwith a philosophical extremism, something close to a «*pseudotheology of the origin*»⁴⁶: against this extremism Löwith rises the Hellenistic ideal of «measure»⁴⁷. On the other hand, those ellenistic philosophical schools are for Strauss a kind of dogmatism, for they never discuss the doctrines of their founders, whereas their “progenitor”, Socrates, was not a dogmatist at all⁴⁸.

3. Conclusion

The latest observations allow us to suggest a few answers to some of the questions raised above.

In the first place, the field to which the two authors refer when speaking of “Antiquity” narrows accordingly to the latest considerations: if the two authors share a broad meaning for the term, which encompasses the entire philosophical thought preceding the Christianity, this meaning seems to specify for Strauss in the person of Socrates (in his ineludible connection with Plato, but also Xenophon and Aristophanes) and for Löwith in what one could call the spirit of the Hellenistic schools. In the second place, the common problem raised by the two authors, that of the crisis of the modern belief in progress and, in turn, of the crisis of Modernity itself, has different answers according to the different questions that spur the reflection of the two.

The appeal to the sense of measure that a vision of cosmos as eternal present is able to inspire against the be-

lief in progress has for Löwith a specific meaning related to his broad interpretation of the modern view of history as oriented to the future. This view represents for Löwith an outcome of Christian millenarism and it is able to induce a certain kind of historical blindness, as tragically manifested by the events in 20th century world history, thanks to the fatalistic attitude of acceptance of what comes to the fore.

If Löwith’s problem is the problem of history, and his answer is a moral – and still historicist – one. He seeks a point of view outside the movement of a history conceived as an infinite improvement in the future in order to judge the present times. However, Löwith seems to be pessimistic in this respect, since we always remain rooted in our times. Things are different for Strauss, whose polemical target is historicism. This does not mean to put history aside: on the contrary, he precisely seeks a correct historical understanding of ancient thought. For Strauss historicism means at least two things: first, every age has its own issues, its own answers and its own way to understand itself, which are not accessible to other ages; secondly, Modernity represents an overall improvement compared to what precedes it. To conclude, Modernity is capable of understanding the authors of the past better than they understand themselves. According to Strauss, this idea can easily lead to a dangerous mixture of relativism and absolutism or dogmatism: the merits of the past are relativized in respect to the absolute superiority of the present time⁴⁹.

To these perspectives Strauss opposes the alternative of a return, understood as a radical and incessant research. This research does not exclude *a priori* the ancient questions and the one who undertakes it does not presume to find final answers. Moreover, for this research is necessary to make those ancient questions again, opening to a critical view on the present time, which could not be reached starting from the elements of the present itself:

Let’s start really *before* the alternative atheism-theism, let’s start really from the beginning and the origin and let’s see if from our efforts there emerges something that “has not already been” or something remote or maybe also something that “has already been”. This is how a skeptical should really express himself, a man who expresses a critical point of view [...].⁵⁰

The alternative between sense of limit and return in respect to the issue of the modern belief in progress, originates from these two different perspectives of inquiry.

Notes

¹ During my presentation, I will mainly refer to the following texts: L. Strauss: *Progress or Return? The Contemporary Crisis in Western Civilization*, lecture given at the Hillel Foundation at the University of Chicago on November 5, 1952, in «Modern Judaism» Vol. 1, 17-45; L. Strauss: *On Collingwood’s Philosophy of History*, in «The Review of Metaphysics», Vol. V, No.4, June 1952; L. Strauss, K. Löwith, *Korrespondenz: Leo Strauss-Karl Löwith*, in *Leo Strauss Gesammelte Schriften Band 3: Hobbes’ politische Wissenschaft und zugehörige Schriften – Briefe*, ed. H. and W. Meier, J. B. Metzler Verlag, Stuttgart 2001, pp. 607-697; my quotation are referred to the italian translation: *Oltre Itaca. La filosofia come emigrazione. Carteggio (1932-1971)*, ed. by C. Altini, M. Rossini, Roma, 2012; K. Löwith, *Das Verhängnis des Fortschritts*, in H. Kuhn, F. Wiedman, *Die Philosophie und die Frage nach dem Fortschritt*, Munich, A. Pustet, 1964; italian translation: *La fatalità del progresso*, in *Storia e fede*, Roma-Bari, 1985 [*The Fatality of Progress*]. I

wasn't able to find an English version of this text, so I refer to the Italian edition.

² For a general overview on the evolution of the concept of progress, its connection with the idea of history and the difference between the ancient and the modern concept of progress, with a focus on its political implications, see C. Meier, R. Koselleck, *Fortschritt*, in R. Koselleck, W. Conze, O. Brunner, *Geschichtliche Grundbegriffe. Historisches Lexikon zur politisch-sozialen Sprache in Deutschland*, Bd. 2, Klett Cotta, Stuttgart 1975.

³ L. Strauss, *Progress or Return?*, cit., p.17, emphasis mine.

⁴ K. Löwith, *La fatalità del progresso*, cit. p. 152.

⁵ *Ivi*, p. 165.

⁶ *Ivi*, p. 167, emphasis of the author.

⁷ L. Strauss, *Progress or return?*, cit., p. 27.

⁸ *Ibidem* and K. Löwith, *La fatalità del progresso*, cit., pp. 154 f.: Löwith localizes this passage in the 1830s, in the aftermath of the industrial revolution with its material benefits.

⁹ L. Strauss, *Progress or return?*, cit., p. 24. Strauss refers here to the following texts: J. Bury, *The Idea of Progress. An Inquiry into its Origin and Growth*, Macmillan and co., London 1920 and J. Baillie, *The Belief in Progress*, Charles Scribner's Sons, New York 1951.

¹⁰ L. Strauss, *Progress or return?*, cit., pp. 24-29.

¹¹ This parallelism, which in 1750 was still an open issue, was the target of the critiques made by Rousseau in his *First Discourse*. See J.-J. Rousseau, *Discours sur les sciences et sur les arts*, in *Œuvres complètes*, ed. by B. Gagnebin et M. Raymond, t. III, Paris, Gallimard, 1964.

¹² The modern confidence in the conquests of rationality has been bitterly proved wrong in the last works of Ernst Cassirer, where he discusses the problem of the exploitation of mythical forms of conscience in Nazi politics and propaganda. See in particular E. Cassirer, *The Myth of the State*, Yale University Press, New Haven and London 1946 and Id., *Symbol, Myth and Culture. Essays and Lectures of Ernst Cassirer 1935-1945*, Yale University Press, New Haven and London 1979.

¹³ See K. Löwith, *La fatalità del progresso*, cit., p. 157 and p. 161.

¹⁴ *Ivi*, p. 155-156.

¹⁵ *Ivi*, p. 156, emphasis of the author. Löwith wrote his essay in 1963, in the middle of the cold war. Looking at his historical situation, he observes that the strive for progress becomes coercion in the case of the arms race, when the two enemies are «forced to a progressive duty of progress», *ivi*, p. 166.

¹⁶ *Ivi*, p.166 s.

¹⁷ *Ivi*, p. 149. See also K. Löwith, *Meaning in History*, Chicago-London 1949. Löwith understands progress through his idea of the secularization of Christian eschatology, thus enlightening the fideistic aspect of the idea of progress. H. Blumenberg criticises the interpretation given in *Meaning in History*, because the two conceptions are heterogeneous: according to Christian eschatology, which is a theological category, there will be a final closure of history in Doomsday; moreover, in this religious conceptual frame, the motor of the entire historical process, God, is outside the process itself. Things are different in the case of progress, which is conceived as an immanent force of history; moreover, history has an infinite time at disposition for its movement. Thus, there is a conceptual tension between the idea of infinite improvement within history and the final closure of history in Christian millenarism. See H. Blumenberg, *Die Legitimität der Neuzeit*, Suhrkamp, Frankfurt am Main, 1966. See also R. M. Wallace, *Progress, Secularization and Modernity: The Löwith-Blumenberg Debate*, «New German Critique», n° 22, Special Issue on Modernism, Winter, 1981, pp. 63-79.

¹⁸ See L. Strauss, *Progress or Return?*, cit., p. 24.

¹⁹ Aristotle, *Politics*, 1257 b 25-28, in *Aristotle* in 23 Volumes, Vol. 21, transl. by H. Rackham. Harvard University Press, Cambridge, MA; William Heinemann Ltd, London 1944.

²⁰ Seneca, *Epistulae morales ad Lucilium*, VII, 64, *On The Philosopher's Task*, in *Moral letters to Lucilius*, in 3 volumes, translated by R.M. Gummere, Loeb Classical Library, London-Cambridge, MA 1920-1925; see also *ivi* V, 45, *On Sophistical Argumentation*: « But whatever the quality of my works may be, read them as if I were still seeking, and were not aware of, the truth, and were seeking it obstinately, too. For I have sold myself to no man; I bear the name of no master. I give much credit to the judgment of great men; but I claim something also for my own. For these men, too, have left to us, not positive discoveries, but problems whose solution is still to be sought». See also Seneca, *Quaestiones Naturales*, VI, 31, in *Physical science in the time of Nero; being a translation of the Quaestiones naturales of Seneca*, transl. by J. Clarke, Macmillan and co., London 1911: «Many discoveries are reserved for the ages still to be, when our memory shall have perished».

²¹ Lucretius, *De rerum naturae*, V, 1452-57, transl. by W.E. Leonard, E.P. Dutton and Co., J.M. Dent and Sons, New York 1916.

²² See K. Löwith, *La fatalità del progresso*, cit., pp. 149 f.

²³ See L. Strauss, *Progress or Return?*, cit., pp. 24 f. As it often happens in straussian text, one ought not to underestimate the importance a reference for its brevity.

²⁴ Aristotle, *Politics*, 1269 a 20 ff, cit.

²⁵ Cfr. *ivi*, 1269 a 5-8, p. 54; see also Plato, *Laws*, 676 a- 677 b and *Tiamaeus* 22 c; see also Seneca, *Quaestiones Naturales*, III, 27. The idea of the limitedness of the time of the world and of men within it is a recurring theme in Lucretius' poem.

²⁶ Lucretius, *De rerum naturae*, V, 1430-1435, cit. See G. Sasso, *Il progresso e la morte. Saggi su Lucrezio*, Bologna, Il Mulino, 1979, pp. 252-267, for an enquiry of the issue of progress in Lucretius. According to Sasso, who focuses his interpretation on the fifth book of the poem, Lucretius looks at progress as an unavoidable and irreversible process, one that have increased the sufferings of humans while improving their knowledge and material conditions. Sasso argues that from the awareness of these sufferings there arises in Lucretius a nostalgic sentiment towards a primitive condition, more indigent but also less unhappy. Lucretius never proposes to go back to this primitive condition, and from this ambivalent sentiment stems, according to the interpreter, the «contradiction of progress» in the work of the latin author.

²⁷ Aeschylus, *Prometheus Bound*, transl. by H.W. Smyth, W. Heinemann, London 1922-26. We can compare this idea with the concern towards the possibilities disclosed by knowledge and techniques in the first stasimon of Sophocles' *Antigone*, quoted above. Hans Jonas analyses these verses in his *Das Prinzip Verantwortung: Versuch einer Ethik für die technologische Zivilisation*, Suhrkamp, Frankfurt am Main 1979. Like Strauss and Löwith, Jonas declares to be one of those who think that «there is still something to learn from classical philosophy» regarding the way of thinking and posing questions; see H. Jonas, *Dem bösen Ende näher. Gespräche über das Verhältnis des Menschen zur Natur*, Suhrkamp, Frankfurt am Main 1993.

²⁸ See K. Löwith, *The Fatality of Progress*, cit., p. 167.

²⁹ This is a very discussed point in the debate on this concept. In his introduction to his work on the ancient idea of progress, L. Edelstein criticises those who deny the presence of a progressist perspective in Antiquity, referring in particular to J. Bury, *The Idea of Progress*, cit. See L. Edelstein, *The Idea of Progress in Classical Antiquity*, Baltimore, John Hopkins Press, 1967.

³⁰ See L. Strauss, *On Collingwood's Philosophy of History*, cit., p. 570: «[...] there was a greater awareness in Greece than elsewhere of the essential difference between the ancestral and the good. On the basis of this insight there existed in classical Greece "a historical consciousness", not merely of "catastrophic changes" but also of changes for the better, of progress, and this consciousness was a consciousness not merely of progress achieved but also of the possibility of future progress».

³¹ See J. Bury, *The Idea of Progress*.

³² For an analysis of this idea in Lucretius see G. Sasso, *Il progresso e la morte. Saggi su Lucrezio*, cit., p. 253. See also K. Löwith, *Meaning in History*. The author contrasts the idea of history in the ancient historians Herodotus, Tucidides and Polybius, which includes the alternance of fortunes and misfortunes for different people, with the idea of history oriented toward future improvement, characteristic of modern philosophies of history.

³³ This kind of generalisation regards also the conception of Modernity.

³⁴ See L. Strauss, K. Löwith, *Oltre Itaca*, cit., not dated, p. 87: according to Strauss, Nietzsche re-uses the idea of the indifference of cosmos regarding human beings, i.e. the standing point of pre-Christian philosophy. However, he gives to this idea a particular pathos, alien to the idea itself. See Lucretius, *De Rerum Naturae*, V, 156-165, cit. for an instance of the ancient idea of the indifference of cosmos: according to the poet, it is madness to think that gods have created world and nature out of benevolence towards human beings. He thus shows his opposition against anthropocentrism and the teleological view of the world.

³⁵ *Ivi*, 20th August 1946, p. 144.

³⁶ To be fair, from Strauss's point of view it seems to be more of Löwith's difficulty to understand what Strauss means rather than a mutual problem.

³⁷ *Ivi*, 15th April, 1935, pp. 110-112: «I grew up so little Jewish from the very beginning that I can understand only with great effort and through different paths - and actually *not* come to terms with - how is it possible to be so *rational* and *ethical* as are, substantially, all the Jews that I know, even the ones who are assimilated, and that thanks to their tradition. [...] The dilemma "Orthodox Jew" or "enlightened political zionist" has never been a problem to me»; see also *ivi*, 25th September 1962, p. 191: «Without Hitler, I would probably never realized that I am Jewish».

³⁸ Cfr. G. Scholem, *Vom Berlin nach Jerusalem. Jugenderinnerungen*, Suhrkamp, Frankfurt am Main 1977; L. Strauss, *Why we remain Jews*.

Can Jewish Faith and History still speak to us?, in *Leo Strauss: Political Philosopher and Jewish Thinker*, ed. K.L. Deutsch and W. Nicgorski, Rowman and Littlefield, Lanham–London 1994; id. *Korrespondenz Leo Strauss-Gerschom Scholem*, cit.

³⁹ See R.G. Collingwood, *The Idea of History*, Clarendon Press, Oxford 1946. Arnaldo Momigliano, in his *Ermeneutica e pensiero politico classico in Leo Strauss*, in *Pagine ebraiche*, Einaudi, Torino 1987, pp. 189–199, summarises the position of the english scholar as follows: «Collingwood [...] asseriva che ogni periodo storico ha un pensiero storico che gli corrisponde e che vale assolutamente per quel periodo: riteneva poi che ogni ricerca storica fosse relativa al presente, cioè a qualcosa per definizione estraneo agli interessi presenti agli uomini del passato», *ivi*, p. 190.

⁴⁰ L. Strauss, *On Collingwood's Philosophy of History*, cit., pp. 585 f.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*

⁴² *Ivi*, p. 583.

⁴³ K. Löwith, *La fatalità del progresso*, cit., pp. 169 f. With a similar awareness, Hans Jonas expresses the urgency to modify the consideration of the natural environment and to assign to men the responsibility of its protection. *Das Prinzip Verantwortung*, cit.

⁴⁴ See L. Strauss, K. Löwith, *Oltre Itaca*, cit., 15th April 1935, p. 112.

⁴⁵ *Ivi*, 13th July 1935, p. 124.

⁴⁶ *Ivi*, 2nd August 1933, p. 92: «what I think is wrong [in Heidegger's *The Self Assertion of the German University and What is Metaphysics?*] it is something that you share with him: the *pseudotheology of the "origin"*, to which one has to lead back the secularized original sin, which is fulfilled in the faith in "destiny". From *here* originates the entire ambiguity of his [Heidegger] claim to the beginning and the origin, as justification of the end and the present "instant"».

⁴⁷ *Ivi*, 13th July 1935, p. 124.

⁴⁸ *Ivi*, 23rd June 1935, p. 118. An example of Strauss's concern is given by the role of Epicurus' philosophy in Lucretius.

⁴⁹ This mixture of relativism and dogmatism can be observed also in the logical circle of historicism as Strauss understands it. See C. Altini, *Storia della filosofia, storiografia e storicismo in R.G. Collingwood, L. Strauss e A. Momigliano*, «Anuari de la Societat Catalana de Filosofia», XVI, 2004/2005, p. 32: «[...] ogni verità è valida solo nel proprio periodo storico [...] lo storicismo manifesta, in modo autocontraddittorio, il proprio carattere metastorico e dogmatico: nell'affermare l'essenziale storicità del pensiero, lo storicismo afferma la propria storicità e quindi il carattere provvisorio della propria validità». A.M. Iacono observes in his forthcoming *Storicismo e storia della filosofia* that for Strauss historicism makes every truth and even men's freedom relative to the historical context and it culminates in nihilism: «mettendo al centro il tema del mutamento, scardina il problema filosofico di ciò che è permanente ed eterno».

⁵⁰ L. Strauss, K. Löwith, *Oltre Itaca*, cit., 5th September 1933, p. 95.